

Agro2Circular

D1.9 – Energy Management Plan (Final Version)

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List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
AE	Assisted extraction
BST	Total Serum Bilirubin
CAES	Compressed Air Energy Storage
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
DO	Dissolved oxygen
EAE	Enzymatic assisted extraction
EC	European Commission
EG	Ethylene glycol
EMP	Energy Management Plan
EMS	Energy Management System
EU	European Union
EVOH	Ethylene vinyl alcohol
GA	Glycolic acid
GS	Green solvents
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
HESS	Hydrogen-based Energy Storage Systems
ICP	Inferior Calorific Power
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear Low-density polyethylene
MAE	Microwave assisted extraction
NAFTA	North American Free Trade Agreement
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OTR	Oxygen Permeability Test
PA	Polyamide
PCA	Protocatechuic acid
PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoate
PHBV	Poly(3-hidroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
PP	Polypropylene
PS	Polystyrene
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
RITE	Regulation on Thermal Installations in Build
SFE	Supercritical fluid extraction
TFF	Tangential Flow Filtration
TLCAN	North American Free Trade Agreement
TPA	Terephthalic acid

TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAE	Ultrasound assisted extraction
UV	Ultraviolet radiation
VFD	Variable Frequency Drive
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds
VSD	Variable Speed Drive

1 Executive summary

This deliverable is an update of D1.8 as a final version and is intended to serve as an Energy Management Plan for the processes and technologies developed in the Agro2Circular project. The aim is that, as their TRL increases to a semi-industrial scale, they become as efficient and sustainable as possible.

In this regard, the deliverable contains the results obtained from the energy requirements analysis of the project's technologies. These requirements include average power load, peak power load, time of use, and life cycle.

To provide a clearer understanding of the energy-consuming processes involved in each demonstrator, a diagram has been developed, as presented in Figure 21, which further illustrates the interaction between the individual demonstrations.

The analysis identified both the quantities of input materials and the output materials (outputs and waste) for each process. The purpose of this was to calculate the energy consumption KPIs in kWh/kg or kWh/l for generating each product, highlighting those with the highest energy consumption. Waste or by-products generated were also identified to assess possible recovery options that could improve process efficiency, such as the generation of water vapour.

As a result, a series of recommendations for improving the energy efficiency of the processes has been identified. To monitor these recommendations, the foundations for creating a Measurement and Verification Plan and a Communication Plan have been established, which will enable both the identification of deviations and transparency in energy performance improvement strategies.

2 Introduction

This document has been prepared within the framework of Task 1.3 of the Agro2Circular project, funded by the European Commission (EC) under the call H2020-LC-GD-2020-3, and contains the Energy Management Plan (EMP) developed for upcycling plants for plastic and organic waste from the agri-food sector.

Within Task 1.3, the goal is to analyse the energy and water consumption of the technologies and processes used in the project to assess process efficiency and identify areas for improvement. The analyses conducted and the conclusions drawn were documented in the deliverable "D1.7 Energy and Water Recommendations" and in "D1.8 Energy Management Plan (Draft)". In D1.7, water and energy consumption of the processes were analysed, presenting methodologies to identify water treatment technologies and energy efficiency strategies to be refined based on feedback from industrial partners.

In D1.8, a more in-depth analysis of the energy performance of the processes was conducted, and an initial energy management plan was presented as they scale to semi-industrial levels.

This deliverable, "D1.9 Energy Management Plan (Final Version)", provides an update of D1.8 with additional information.

This Energy Management Plan is based on the project demonstrators and aims to assess the energy performance of each process, identifying improvement potential for consideration during scaling. The document includes a series of best practices for optimising energy consumption in the demonstrators at an industrial scale.

The analyses conducted here will be cross-referenced with energy studies to be carried out on the Demos as part of the work to be performed in WP6.

3 State of the Art

This section addresses the analysis and evaluation of energy consumption in the plastics sector, as well as its relationship with waste recovery methods and current regulations. Firstly, it examines energy consumption in the current plastics market, highlighting the energy demands associated with the production and processing of these materials. Following this, plastic consumption and recycling are reviewed, taking into account both the environmental impact and current technological trends in the reuse of these products.

Subsequently, an overview of energy consumption in the waste recovery sector is provided, detailing the various recycling and plastic production methodologies, the energy costs involved in their manufacture, and the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used to measure energy efficiency in this context. Key objectives and targets for optimising energy consumption in the industry are also explored.

Additionally, the concept of an Energy Management Plan is introduced, aiming to lay the groundwork for greater energy efficiency in industrial operations. Finally, the analysis is complemented by a review of the regulatory framework governing the sector, providing a comprehensive understanding of the legal requirements and current policies surrounding energy consumption and plastic waste management.

3.1 Energy consumption in current plastic market

Table 1 shows the primary energy consumption for the production of typical petroleum-derived polymers. These data result from a comprehensive approach to evaluating energy consumption.

Table 1. Primary energy consumption in production of selected plastics. [1]

Polymer	Energy consumption [MJ/kg]			Raw material consumption (petrol) [kg/kg]	Calorific value [MJ/kg]
	Total	From petroleum	From other sources of energy than petroleum		
Polyethylene	70	55	15	1.06-1.35	43
Polypropylene	73	58	15	1.11-1.40	44
Polystyrene	80	55	22	1.06-1.54	40
Polycarbonate	107	36	71	0.69-2.05	31 ¹⁾
Polyvinyl chloride	53	24	29	0.46-1.02	18

The indicator "crude oil energy consumption" includes the energy contained in hydrocarbon fractions (obtained from crude oil), which serve as the raw material for polymer production. This energy is referred to as feedstock energy. Additionally, it accounts for the energy from crude oil or its transformation products used as fuel in processing stages where monomers are produced, leading to the creation of standardised plastics.

The value of the indicator “energy consumption from non-oil energy carriers” consists of energy consumption derived from solid fossil fuels (coal), gaseous fuels (natural gas), and renewable energy sources.

The calorific value of plastic represents the amount of heat generated during the complete combustion of a unit mass of plastic. The ratio between the calorific value of plastic and the total energy consumption in plastic production indicates the portion of invested energy that can be recovered through the thermal treatment of plastic waste.

3.2 Plastic consumption and recycling

Plastic can be defined as a material consisting of a polymer (a substance consisting of molecules characterized by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units [2]) to which additives or other substances may have been added, and which can function as a main structural component of final products, with the exception of natural polymers that have not been chemically modified [3].

Plastics may have different physical properties that make them behave differently when heated. Depending on this, they can be classified into [4]:

- Thermoplastics. Thermoplastics melt at high temperatures, thus being possible to mould them. Once they cool down, they harden and keep the final shape that they had been given. This process can be repeated more than once, something that makes them especially good for recycling.
- Thermosets. Thermosets are plastics that can only be melted down once. They adopt the shape that is given to them and once they harden, they will burn if heated up again.
- Elastomers. Elastomers have elastic properties that allow them to recover their original shape after being deformed. Elastomers' molecules are rather weakly bonded, when they are stretched, molecules align, returning to their initial state once force is no longer applied.

Besides this classification based on physical properties, the classification using label numbers is widely used to identify the type of plastic a product is made of and whether it can be recycled. This classification is the following [5]:

1. PET or PETE.
2. HDPE.
3. PVC.
4. LDPE or PEBD.
5. PP.
6. PS.
7. Other plastics.

From the previous list, plastics 1 – 5 can be recycled, while PS, on the other hand, generally cannot be recycled but it can be used to produce plant pots or used in building materials. This recycling capability is something of great importance, considering that due to plastic's versatility and ease of modification, it has been widely used in the last decades.

There are different personalities who have had a huge importance in the early development of plastics: Alexander Parkes invented an early plastic in 1855 that is now known as celluloid [6], the first synthetic polymer was invented in 1869 by John Wesley Hyatt [7] and it was not until 1907 that Leo Baekeland invented Bakelite, the first fully synthetic plastic.

This new material offered a world of possibilities due to its properties such as durability, insulation capability, heat resistance, and ease of production. As a result, global plastic production in 1950 was 1,3 million tons [8].

By the year 2010, 265 million tons were produced worldwide and in 2021 we reached 391 million tons. From this gigantic amount, less than 10% is part of a circular economic model [9].

Figure 1. Distribution of the global plastics production. Source: [9]

Worldwide plastic production is expected to keep growing, reaching 417 million tons by the year 2030 [10], as its properties make it a perfect material for many different applications.

Figure 2. Distribution of plastics production in the world in 2019. [11]

In 2019, China reached 31% of global plastic production. With Asia in the lead, they are followed by NAFTA (North American Free Trade Agreement) and then Europe, with 16%.

As for the European Union, as can be seen in Figure 3, plastic production in 2022 reached almost 59 million tons.

Figure 3. Distribution of European Union Production in 2022. [12]

Each EU inhabitant generated an average of 36.1 kg of plastic packaging waste in 2021. The volume of plastic packaging waste generated per inhabitant increased by around 29% (+8.1 kg per person) between 2010 and 2021.

The total plastic waste produced in the EU in 2021 was 16.13 million tons. Some 6.56 million tons of plastic waste was recycled.

Figure 4 shows the amount of waste produced and recycled in the European Union from 2011-2021.

Fuente: Eurostat [env_waspac] - datos más recientes disponibles (2021)

Figure 4. Plastics waste produced and recycled in EU. [13]

Regarding the use of plastic in the agricultural field, it started with the use of PVC and cellophane in order to cover greenhouses. Materials such as glass that used to be used to cover greenhouses, or paper and straw that were used for soil mulching have lost the fight against plastics [14]. In 2010, 15,6 million tons of plastics were used in agriculture alone, nearly 4% of the global production. In Europe, plastic demand in agriculture was about 3,1% of total plastic demand in Europe, being LDPE, HDPE, PP, PVC and other thermosets and thermoplastics the most demanded plastics in the agricultural sector [15].

In this context, ensuring that plastics are recycled is key in order to promote circularity. Plastic residues can be used to produce new plastic products or even burnt as fuels to produce energy, being the achievement of a circular economy the goal that should be followed [16]. This circular approach is shown in Figure 5 where it can be seen that plastic products should be produced partly from recycled materials and partly from new ones, used, reused and repaired and then collected and recycled when possible, re-starting the cycle.

Figure 5. Circularity of plastics scheme. Source: [17]

As a result, a correct waste collection, treatment and recycling methodology must be implemented to assure the circularity of the process, to make sure that raw materials demand decreases, to improve the process viability and, ultimately, to achieve sustainability.

It is highly important to understand the recycling process, from the moment in which waste is collected to the moment in which recyclates are produced and prepared to be used again. All this process has a certain energy consumption and subproducts associated and reducing these as much as possible is a must.

3.3 Overview of energy consumption in the plastic waste recovery sector

3.3.1 Recycling and plastic production methods.

Rather than using plastic waste to produce energy, as this process involves burning it and thus it has CO₂ and other pollutant emissions, the goal should be recycling as much as possible. Governments in Europe seem to have realized that, as the evolution of plastic waste use (Figure 6) shows: the amount of plastic recycled doubled between 2006 and 2020.

The total amount of plastic packaging waste sent to recycling facilities has more than doubled since 2006. However, 6.9 million tons of plastic packaging waste were still sent to landfill and 10.2 million tons to energy recovery. For the first time since 2006, the amount of plastic packaging waste sent to energy recovery decreased.

Figure 6. Evolution of plastic waste treatment in the European Union. [18]

A general classification for plastic recycling is the following [19]:

- Primary recycling.
- Secondary recycling.
- Tertiary recycling.
- Energy recovery.

Primary recycling, also known as closed-loop recycling, is defined by [20] as the process of taking uncontaminated discarded plastics and directly turning them into the same “new” product, ideally without loss of properties. An example of this would be collecting used bottles to clean and reuse them.

Secondary recycling refers to mechanical recycling, in which polymers don’t change chemically but are physically reprocessed and used for a different purpose from the prior one. This would be the case of, for instance, making granules out of waste tires to use them on playground floors or on artificial grass football fields.

Tertiary recycling, also known as chemical recycling, uses chemical processes to break down the polymer into value-added commodities that can be later on used as feedstock for the production of fuels and polymers. In this case, there is not a direct reuse of the plastic per se, but a treatment to obtain a new raw material that can be used to produce new plastics.

Finally, energy recovery is used when none of the previous options are available because of the low quality of the plastic or the degradation of its properties. By burning the plastic, some of its energy can be recovered and used in other processes, but there are important

CO₂ emissions and once it is burned, no further uses can be achieved, so this option does not contribute to closing the loop in a circular economy.

Regarding recycling methodologies, we can speak of 3 main ones [21]. Some of them have already been mentioned when speaking about the general recycling classification:

- Mechanical recycling.
- Dissolution recycling.
- Chemical recycling.

Mechanical recycling recovers plastic by means of heat and shear. Mechanical recycling has traditionally been the only method to recycle plastic waste [22]. This process does not disrupt the polymer chains except due to possible degradation of the polymer itself. Thermoset materials cannot be recycled through these methods, as they don't melt when heated, so it would only be possible to tear them down to pieces that could be later on used as fillers or for other purposes. Mechanical recycling is key for plastics sustainability. However, mechanical processes are limited by cost, loss of mechanical properties of the plastics and inconsistent quality products.

Authors in bibliography suggest that the length of polymer chain and the degree of branching influence degradation kinetics, and that these variables should be kept in mind when considering different recycling methods [23] [24] [25]. Mechanical recycling is often carried out through extrusion: waste plastic is regranulated, then it passes through rotating screws to induce thermal softening of plasticization. Finally, it passes through temperature-controlled barrel sections to produce the extrudate. Despite the fact that this process is highly widespread, operating conditions lead to chain degradation, reducing chains' length and negatively affecting its mechanical properties and processability [10]. As a result, usually new material is added in order to keep plastic properties; for instance, when recycling PET bottles, the new to recycled material ratio is often 70/30 by weight.

Dissolution recycling, also known as physical recycling, uses chemical products and heat to dissolve polymers into a solution of polymers and separate them from the rest of the waste and additives. By doing so, it is possible to separate materials without breaking any chain, and including impurities in new materials is prevented, thus allowing the recycling of food related materials that otherwise would not be recyclable because of food scents [26].

Alkanes are used as solvents to perform these processes as they share molecular similarities with products to be treated and can withstand high temperatures and pressures. The process is carried out in 2 steps: in the first one, plastic is submerged in the solvent and everything is heated. High pressure keeps the solvent in liquid state and high temperatures dissolve the impurities from the plastic into the solvent, which is later on drained. In the second step, a fresh batch of solvent is fed to the system, rising temperature to dissolve the plastic itself and then removing it, leaving only undissolved impurities. Then the solution is cooled down until plastic solidifies, removing the solvent away [26] [27]. The main benefit from this method is the fact that no substantial difference in properties from the starting material and the recycled one is found. Besides, the used solvent can be recovered and recirculated within the recycling system, which also reduces process' costs. Finally, this technology does not require extensive pre-treatment and it obtains high conversion rates making it a very promising technology [28].

Chemical recycling manages to produce monomers or new raw materials by changing the chemical structure of plastic waste through chemical processes such as cracking, gasification or depolymerization, excluding energy recovery and incineration. Its main advantage is its capability to deal with complex plastic waste streams, like films or laminates, that would otherwise end up in landfill or incineration processes [29]. By doing so, the amount of fossil resources required is reduced, moving us towards a circular economy with lower dependence from non-renewable resources. Chemical recycling can be divided into solvolysis, pyrolysis and gasification [30].

Solvolysis includes processes such as alcoholysis, hydrolysis or aminolysis, that is the decomposition of polymers by using alcohols, water, ammonia, etc. Through these processes, using solvents, temperature and pressure oligomers and monomers are produced [31], breaking C – X bonds, where X are hetero (non-carbon) atoms, such as O, N, P, S, Si or halogen among others [32].

Pyrolysis technology manages to convert plastics into high value fuels and chemicals. The main difference of pyrolysis compared to incineration or gasification is the absence of O₂ in the process, reducing CO₂ and toxic pollutants emissions [33], but this process involves high temperatures (around 500°C) too. Plastic waste is vaporized in a reactor and then condensed to produce pyrolysis oil along with fuel gas and char, and hydrocarbons [34].

In gasification, a gasifying agent such as steam, oxygen and air is applied to plastic waste at temperatures between 500 and 1300°C, producing syngas that can be later on used to produce products or as a fuel [35].

3.3.2 Energy costs in the plastic fabrication sector.

One of the main issues to be considered in plastic recycling, once the proper methodology to recycle it depending on the quality of the plastic has been chosen is the process' cost.

During the recycling process, not only energy is consumed, but other resources like water or new plastic can be required too. As a result, the global warming potential of the recycling process is negative, as the process prevents the production of new plastic, but resources' costs can be high, making companies unwilling to invest in recycling.

Table 2 shows energy and water consumption for different virgin and recycled plastics. It is important to note that both energy and water requirements for recycled plastic are lower than those required for new ones.

Table 2. Energy and water requirements for virgin and recycled plastic production [36].

	Energy requirement (GJ/ton)	Water requirement (m ³ /ton)
Virgin PET	82,7	66
Virgin HDPE	76,7	32
Virgin LDPE	78,1	47
Virgin PVC	56,7	46

Virgin PP	73,4	43
Virgin PS	87,4	140
Recycled plastics	8-55	3,5

Besides energy and water costs (the main inputs of the process, apart from waste plastic), another point of huge importance that needs to be considered is the required investment to build a working plastic recycling plant and its cost of operation and maintenance. These costs are usually known as CAPEX (capital expenditure) and OPEX (operational expenditure). While CAPEX includes all actives acquired by the company (acquisition of machines, terrains, buildings, initial investment...), OPEX includes those expenses related to daily operation and services' payments (electricity and water costs, employees' payment, machines' maintenance...). An estimation of these costs can be seen on Table 3:

Table 3. Required investment in recycling technologies [36].

	Investment cost to process 1 ton/day	Annual operation and maintenance to process 1 ton/day
Mechanical recycling	1.795 – 8.980 €	449 – 1.347 €
Chemical recycling (pyrolysis)	769.752 €	449 – 898 €
Chemical recycling (gasification)	345.804 €	11.091 €
Incineration	455.000 – 480.000 €	40.000 €

The costs in Table 3 give an idea of the amount of money required to install a plastic recycling plant. Regarding energy consumption, according to [37], the plastic production industry is responsible for nearly 5% of the total electricity consumption of the manufacturing industry in Spain. Thus, it is vastly important to introduce elements and strategies that help reduce energy consumption, improve energy efficiency and, if possible, adopt renewable energies to reduce the activity's carbon footprint.

Table 4. Energy consumption in the plastic fabrication industry, Spain [37].

	Electricity (m€)	Gas (m€)	Diesel (m€)	Fuel (m€)	Other petroleum products (m€)	Biofuels (m€)	Heat (m€)	Total energy consumption (m€)
2015	333.002	33.840	14.791	29	2.453	0	1.394	385.509
2017	309.342	48.417	12.982	742	3.047	584	1.190	376.303
2019	345.067	34.843	20.634	1.116	1.124	6	1.439	404.229

A possible strategy to improve energy efficiency and ultimately to reduce energy consumption in a company is the use of key performance indicators, its monitoring and comparison to previously established goals.

3.3.3 Key Performance Indicators' definition

A key performance indicator (KPI) is a critical quantitative indicator of progress towards an intended result [38]. In order to successfully adopt the use of key performance indicators, a company needs to analyse the process in which this methodology will be applied, so that the most relevant variables are identified and the focus is set on them. Once the process is understood and key variables identified, it is needed to determine which of them can be quantified and monitored so that more or less regular feedback on how the process is advancing is obtained. Then, targets need to be set, and measures need to be taken to effectively track the value of these variables, comparing them to the established targets to get to know the situation in which the process is.

3.3.4 Objectives and goals

As it was explained in the previous paragraph, in order to effectively adopt the use of KPIs, establishing objectives and goals is required. Objectives and goals need to be specific, measurable and achievable:

- Specific goals rather than undefined ones are properly chosen, based on evidence of their effect on the process, and they define clearly the part of the process in which they are expected to be reached. By doing so, vain efforts trying to reach impossible results or to achieve those results in parts of the process where they are not required are avoided.
- Results need to be measurable so that it is possible to compare KPIs with the obtained result and determine how near or far results are from the desirable goals. Furthermore, by using measurable results and KPIs, objectivity is gained since there is no room for opinions when comparing 2 values.
- Finally, goals need to be achievable, it does not make sense establishing goals that cannot be reached, obtaining bad results when comparing KPIs with the expected value. For instance, reducing the process energy consumption by around 20% could be possible if certain energy efficiency measures were taken, but reducing it to 100% is not realistic.

3.4 Concept of an Energy Management Plan (EMP)

An EMP is a specific document or set of documents usually elaborated to serve as a support tool for the implementation of an Energy Management System (EMS). These documents serve as a long-term planning resource that outlines the goals, strategies, and actions that have been set to optimize energy consumption.

An EMP must include, at a minimum, an energy reduction goal and an implementation plan to achieve that goal, and usually includes the methodology to verify the achievement of the proposed reduction, for example, by calculating a baseline of energy consumption.

An Energy Management Plan must be followed taking continuous improvement as a philosophy. In that sense, the Plan-do-check-act (PDCA) cycle is proposed in most of the standards for implementing an EMS such as the Standard ISO 50001. The following figure shows the philosophy of the PDCA cycle:

Figure 7. Plan-do-check-act cycle

Different stages of the PDCA cycle and actions to be taken in each of them are shown in Table 5:

Table 5. Energy consumption in the plastic fabrication industry, Spain. Source: [37]

Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish the objectives and scope of the Energy Management Plan. - Conduct an energy assessment or audit to determine the current energy consumption and identify areas for improvement. - Set specific energy goals, targets, and performance indicators. - Develop strategies and action plans to achieve the energy objectives, considering energy-saving measures, equipment upgrades, employee training, etc.
Do	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement the strategies and action plans defined in the planning stage. - Allocate necessary resources, including budget, personnel, and technology, to support the implementation. - Execute energy-saving measures, optimize processes, install energy-efficient equipment, and integrate renewable energy sources as applicable. - Ensure proper documentation and communication of the implemented actions.
Check	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor and measure energy consumption and performance against the established goals and targets. - Collect and analyse energy data, such as utility bills, meter readings, and process-specific measurements. - Compare the actual energy performance with the planned objectives and identify any deviations or gaps.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct regular energy audits and assessments to evaluate the effectiveness of the implemented measures.
Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Take corrective actions and make necessary adjustments based on the findings of the check stage. - Address energy performance gaps and non-compliance with energy objectives. - Continuously review and improve energy management strategies and processes. - Capture lessons learned, share best practices, and update the Energy Management Plan accordingly. - Engage employees and stakeholders in the improvement process and encourage their participation and feedback.

3.5 Regulatory framework

The following list summarizes the most relevant regulation and standards applicable when elaborating Energy Management Plans:

Table 6. List of most relevant regulations and standards for EMPs.

ISO 50001	ISO 50001 is probably the most common standard followed when implementing an Energy Management System (EMS). This international standard offers a framework for organizations to develop energy policies, establish objectives, systems and processes to continuously improve energy performance including energy efficiency, use and consumption.
Standard EN 16001	While ISO 50001 has largely replaced it, EN 16001 was the precursor to the ISO standard. It provides a framework for energy management, including establishing energy policies, setting objectives, conducting energy reviews, and implementing energy-saving measures
Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU)	This directive pursues the objective of achieving the EU's energy savings targets. This directive requires member states of the EU to implement measures to promote energy efficiency in the public and private sectors and includes provisions for energy audits and EMS.
Industry-Specific Regulations	Depending on the sector, there may be specific regulations and guidelines related to energy management. As the technologies' implementation of this project takes place in Spain, Spanish regulations in relation with energy efficiency have been checked. The main regulations are listed below:

-
- Royal Decree 56/2016, of February 12, which transposes Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of October 25, 2012, on energy efficiency, regarding energy audits, accreditation of service providers and energy auditors, and the promotion of energy supply efficiency: This regulation transposes the European Union Energy Efficiency Directive and establishes the requirements for mandatory energy audits for large companies, as well as the accreditation criteria for energy service providers and energy auditors.
 - Royal Decree 1027/2007, of July 20, approving the Regulation on Thermal Installations in Buildings (RITE): Although this regulation primarily focuses on energy efficiency in buildings, it also establishes requirements for industrial thermal installations, including aspects related to energy efficiency in industrial processes and air conditioning systems.
 - Law 18/2014, of October 15, approving urgent measures for growth, competitiveness, and efficiency: This law includes specific measures and programs to promote energy efficiency and energy savings in various sectors, including the industry.

4 List of Processes

All the processes in A2C project aim to upgrade and recycle waste from the agri-food chain: such as organic compounds from fruit and vegetables, post-industrial food contaminated plastics from packaging and the agricultural barrier films.

The processes can be divided into two main branches: (1) those focused on the upcycling of fruit and vegetable waste and (2) those focused on the recycling of plastics used in industry for food packaging and as agriculture barrier films.

Within group (1) are processes 1 and 2 and in group (2) are the rest. These processes can be visualised schematically in the following diagram and table, which have been previously presented in D1.8:

Figure 8. Agro2Circular diagram flow.

Table 7. Information relating to the processes studied.

PROCESS	DESCRIPTION	TASKS INVOLVED	SUBTASK	START MONTH	END MONTH	START TRL	END TRL	PILOT SCALE UP
1	Green hybrid technologies for extraction of bioactive substances from agrifood wastes	2.1	-	2	16	5	7	Route 1: Extraction 100 kg/h and purification 15 kg Route 2: Extraction 50 kg/h and purification 15 kg
		2.2	2.2.1					
			2.2.2					
		2.3	2.3.1	8	16			
2	New food, nutraceuticals & cosmetic formulations using extracts from agrifood wastes	2.3	2.3.2	8	16	5	7	Delivery systems up to 1 kg
		2.4	-					
3	Identification and sorting of multilayer materials	3.2	3.2.1	2	22	4	6	Multilayers sorting flow rates of 25 kg/h
			3.2.2					
			3.2.3					
4	Separation of aluminium (Al) from complex multilayer structures	3.3	3.3.1	3	22	5	7	Pilot plant up to 20 kg batches
			3.3.2					
			3.3.3					
5	PET/PE enzymatic depolymerisation	3.4	3.4.1	3	22	4	6	Pilot plant: 50-80 kg of PET/PE pre-treated, 30 L reactor for enzymes production and a 50 L bioreactor and a
			3.4.2					
			3.4.3					

PROCESS	DESCRIPTION	TASKS INVOLVED	SUBTASK	START MONTH	END MONTH	START TRL	END TRL	PILOT SCALE UP
6	Plastics decontamination	3.1	3.1.1	2	9	5	7	1.000 L/day of wastewater filtered and 500 kg of plastics decontamination
			3.1.2					
		3.5	3.5.1	7	22			
7	Aluminium recycling and chemical modification	3.5	3.5.2	7	22	4	6	Pilot scale up to 1 kg
			3.5.3					
8	Upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (TPA, EG) by cell factories	5.1	5.1.1	13	22	4	6	Pilot scale up to 30 L
9	PHBV and C-50 carotenoids development by <i>Hfx mediterranei</i> haloarchaea cell factory	5.1	5.1.2	13	22	4	6	Pilot scale up to 100 L and extraction process to 1-3L
10	High barrier compounds by extensional flow mixing and compatibilisation	5.2	5.2.1	13	22	5	7	Pilot scale up to 1.000 kg of capacity
			5.2.2					

Each of the technologies to be studied are explained in more detail below:

(1) Green hybrid extraction, purification & stabilisation routes for the obtaining of high valuable bioactives

The aim is to achieve high extraction yields and high purity bioactives with high stability for new foods, nutraceuticals & cosmetics.

- A2C technologies for the recycling of the organic agrifood wastes:

Agrifood industry food waste

Figure 9. Flowchart of the extraction and upcycling of food waste from the agrifood industry.

(2) Synergistic combination of sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination & mechanical recycling for the multilayers recycling and biotransformation processes & extensional flow mixing for the upcycling of the recycled multilayers.

The aim is to obtain a range of high barrier recyclable compounds as alternative to current multilayers in food packaging & agriculture, PHBV bioplastics compounds for biodegradable food packaging & agriculture and carotenoids for cosmetics

Multilayer aseptic bags upcycling

Figure 10. Multilayer aseptic bags upcycling.

Multilayer soil disinfection films

Figure 11. Multilayer soil disinfection films.

4.1 Process 1: Green hybrid technologies for extraction of bioactive substances from agrifood wastes

4.1.1 Description

This process is in the initial phase within the block of the upgrading of fruit and vegetable waste. The process aims to develop the best extraction route of the bioactive substances

from the organic wastes. The raw material used for these extraction routes is derived from waste produced by agrifood industries. The types of residues used are shown below:

Table 8. The fruits and vegetables wastes used for revalorization.

Product	Waste (% of generation)
Citrus	Peel, pulp, skins, seeds (50-60%)
Apples	Peel, seeds and cores, exhausted pulp (10-15%)
Grapes	Pomace (peel, seeds, stems and pulp residues) and grape remains (25%)
Artichoke	Leaves and bracts (60-65%)
Cauliflower	Stems, florets not suitable for marketing, and leaves (40%)
Broccoli	Stems and florets not suitable for marketing, leaves (25-30%)

First of all, this raw material is conditioned, choosing a specific treatment according to the type of waste and its state. Among the treatments used are: drying, crushing, grinding, filtering, etc. In this way, concentration and attack surface are increased, which makes the subsequent extraction stages more effective and shortens the time required.

Once the raw material has been conditioned, the bioactive compound extraction stage is carried out. The route chosen will depend on the results obtained in the laboratory scale. After extraction, on the one hand, the solid part is obtained, which accounts for approximately 20% and contains the fibres, and on the other hand, the liquid part, which accounts for the rest (80%) and contains the phenolic compounds and carotenoids.

To carry out the concentration of the compounds, a purification route is carried out to achieve a suitable composition of each compound. These routes and expected results can be found below:

Table 9. Extraction and purification technologies.

Extraction route	Purification tech.	Expected results
Green solvents + ultrasounds assisted extraction	Membrane Filtration	Dietary fibre (Yield \geq 60%, Purity \geq 70%)
	Membrane Filtration + Adsorption	Phenolic compounds & Carotenoids (Yield \geq 60%, Purity \geq 70%)
Green solvents + enzymatic hydrolysis + MW assisted extraction	Membrane Filtration	Dietary fibre (Yield \geq 70%, Purity \geq 80%)
	Membrane Filtration + Adsorption	Phenolic compounds & Carotenoids (Yield \geq 70%, Purity \geq 80%)

4.1.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 12. Process 1 flow diagram.

4.2 Process 2: New food, nutraceuticals & cosmetic formulations using extracts from agrifood wastes.

4.2.1 Description

The objective of this process is the production of a range of new formulations using the bioactive substances extracted from wastes for their application in cosmetics, nutraceuticals and food.

This process is a continuation of process one. Once the extraction is done, the aim is to separate and stabilise the most interesting compounds for use in nutraceutical, food and cosmetic formulations. In order to do this, filtration is first carried out, separating the solid part from the liquid. The solid part, which accounts for approximately 20% of the total, contains the fibres and the liquid part, which accounts for the remaining part, contains the phenolic compounds and carotenoids.

To stabilise the fibres, the solid part is placed in an oven for dehydration. To obtain the phenolic compounds and carotenoids, a concentration stage is first carried out in which part of the water contained is evaporated, and then, depending on their subsequent use, different stabilisation and conservation processes have been tried out, such as: atomisation, freeze-drying and spray-drying.

The scaling up of this process aims to obtain prototypes for food & nutraceuticals (3000L vegetable desserts, 2000L enriched juices, 20.000 kg-juices & jams, 1000L nutraceuticals), and cosmetic (1 kg antioxidants formulations).

4.2.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 13. Process 2 flow diagram.

The power, pressures and times indicated in the flow diagram are those expected in the pilot plant, due to the fact that these values are impossible to quantify through laboratory scale tests because almost all the stages are manual and discontinuous.

4.3 Process 3: Identification and sorting of multilayer materials

4.3.1 Description

The aim of this process is the use of optical sorting to separate the metallised fraction from the multilayer food packaging plastic waste, by a synergistic combination of technologies resulting in the separation of the different multilayers into the fractions:

1. Metallised fraction (PE/met-PET/PE and PE/Al/PA/PE)
2. Non metallised fraction (PE/EVOH, PE, PE/EVOH/PA)

4.3.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 14. Process 3 flow diagram.

4.4 Process 4: Separation of aluminium (Al) from complex multilayer structures

4.4.1 Description

The objective of this process is the physical separation of the aluminium from the multilayers based on delamination technology. The result is to obtain separated flows of LDPE/PET, LLDPE/PET, LDPE, PE/PA and Al.

To carry out this process, a large number of equipment is involved.

4.4.1 Process flow diagram

The flow diagram of this process is considered as confidential information.

4.5 Process 5: PET/PE enzymatic depolymerisation

4.5.1 Description

The objective of this project is the depolymerisation of the PE/PET multilayers by a synergic strategy of customisation of enzymes and plastic wastes pre-treatments.

In order for the degradative enzyme to perform its function most effectively, it is first pre-treated by applying heat and humidity while exposing in a UV chamber with a Xenon-arc lamp to increase PE polarity and hydrolyse PET. The UV exposure method will reach 90°C of BST and the Xenon lamp irradiance is going to be 60 W/m² (300nm to 400 nm broadband). Finally, it is processed through an extruder and then through a granulator.

At the same time, in parallel, the enzyme capable of degrading PE/PET is produced in a reactor (in the pilot plant it will be 30 L). Once produced, the mixture will be mixed with the pre-treated PE/PET waste in the appropriate proportion and the enzymatic biodegradation will start (in the pilot plant it will be carried out in a 50 L reactor).

The result is water, which will be treated and recirculated, the enzymes, which will be recovered and the reaction products: TPA & EG products, which will serve as input for further processes.

4.5.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 15. Process 5 flow diagram.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

4.6 Process 6: Plastics decontamination

4.6.1 Description

The aim of this process is to eliminate 99% of the contaminants that the plastics may contain. This decontamination is carried out in several stages, the first consists of a preliminary washing with water, which will eliminate solvent traces, ground, chemicals and organic contaminants. The water used for washing will be collected and fully recovered through various filtration and treatment processes. Subsequently, a centrifugation process is carried out to remove the water content, followed by a granulation process to achieve the appropriate size. Finally, a vacuum extrusion process is carried out to remove all the Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) and odours.

4.6.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 16. Process 6 flow diagram.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

4.7 Process 7: Aluminium recycling and chemical modification

4.7.1 Description

The objective of this process is the aluminium purification and treatment for reuse. For this purpose, aluminium from the physical separation will be chemically modified. The result of the chemical modification is that the aluminium achieves optimal compatibility and dispersion in a polyethylene matrix. Two strategies will be investigated:

- i) direct binding of an organic-ligand and further modification with a polyethylene compatible shell
- ii) a two-step procedure where the particles are modified with aluminium oxide/silicon oxide in a first step, followed by a well-established polymer-shell synthesis protocol.

Finally, the aluminium is dispersed in a matrix of LDPE/EVOH/LDPE and LDPE/PA/LDPE through an extrusion process. These blends will be analysed by serial block-face scanning electron microscopy to obtain real 3D distribution, orientation and concentration of filler materials.

4.7.2 Process flow diagram

PROCESS 7: Aluminium recycling and chemical modification

Figure 17. Process 7 flow diagram.

4.8 Process 8: Upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (TPA, EG) by cell factories

4.8.1 Description

The objective of this process is the upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (TPA, EG) by biotransformation to obtain high added value building blocks for cosmetic:

- Terephthalic acid-TPA. Result: protocatechuic acid.
- Ethylene glycol-EG. Result: glycolic acid.

The best results will be scale up at 10L reactors.

4.8.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 18. Process 8 flow diagram.

4.9 Process 9: PHBV and C-50 carotenoids development by *Hfx. mediterranei* haloarchaea cell factory

4.9.1 Description

The objective is the production of PHBV bioplastics and carotenoids by a cell factory. The by-products of the previous cell factories in combination with organic waste from the agri-food industry will be used as nutrients. The result is PHBV for its application in flexible packaging and agricultural films, carotenoids for cosmetics applications.

The work to be carried out to increase the TRL of the process are: upgrading the fermentation of the haloarchaea from lab scale to pilot scale of 100 L and upgrading the extraction process at pilot scale of 1-3 L.

4.9.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 19. Process 9 flow diagram.

4.10 Process 10: High barrier compounds by extensional flow mixing and compatibilisation

4.10.1 Description

The objective of this process is the development of PHBV bioplastics compounds through a synergistic strategy of compatibilisation and extensional flow mixing generation during the extrusion process to develop morphology-controlled blends.

The neat PHBV range obtained will be formulated and compounded for their application in the flexible food packaging and agricultural films development.

4.10.2 Process flow diagram

Figure 20. Process 10 diagram flow.

5 Relation between Processes and Demo Sites

To clarify the relationship between processes and demonstrators, a table is presented categorising processes according to their corresponding demonstrators.

Additionally, a general diagram is provided to illustrate the interrelationship between the various processes and demonstrator groups.

Table 10. Relationship between Processes and Demonstrators

Demonstrators	Processes
1	3, 4, 5
6 & 8	10
7 & 9	4, 6, 7
2	8
3	1, 2
4	1, 2
5	9

Figure 21. Flowchart of the relationship between processes and diagrams.

To facilitate understanding, the demonstrators have been grouped into five categories, according to their interrelation and the processes involved.

5.1 Brief description of the demonstrators

5.2 Demos 1 and 6-9

Figure 22. Diagram of the Relationship between Demonstrators 1 & 6-9.

Figure 22 illustrates the interrelationship among Demonstrators 1, 6, 7, 8 and 9, which operate in a coordinated manner.

Starting with Demonstrator 1, after an initial pretreatment, optical sorting will be employed to separate the metallised fraction from the multi-layered plastic packaging waste (Process 3). Subsequently, these will undergo a physical separation process for aluminium based on delamination technology (Process 4), which will divide them into two groups. The PET/PE multi-layers will be subjected to pretreatment and enzymatic degradation, producing reaction products such as TPA, and EG (Process 5). The aluminium, on the other hand, will be purified and treated for reuse, proceeding directly to Demonstrator 9 (Process 4).

In relation to Demonstrators 7 and 9, the LDPE multi-layers will undergo a decontamination process (Process 6). This process will be carried out independently in Demonstrators 7 and 9. Demonstrator 9 receives the aluminium from Demonstrator 1, subjects it to a modification process (Process 4), and then directs it to the extrusion stage, where the recycled aluminium will be used for food packaging and agricultural applications (Process 9). Similarly, Demonstrator 7 will not require the use of aluminium but will undergo a compatibilisation process, and its final product will also be used for food packaging and agricultural applications (Process 6).

In Demonstrators 6 and 8, the bioplastic compounds of PHBV, obtained from Demonstrator 5, will be developed through a synergistic strategy of compatibilisation and blending during the extrusion process. This aims to produce biodegradable pellets intended for plastic packaging and agricultural films (Process 10).

5.3 Demo 2

In Demonstrator 2, the products obtained in Demonstrator 1 (EG and TPA) will be used alongside lemon peel, which has been enzymatically treated in Demonstrator 3, with the aim of recycling them through biotransformation (Process 8).

Figure 23. Diagram of the Relationship for Demonstrator 2.

For each input, a distinct process will be carried out:

- EG (ethylene glycol) will undergo a centrifugation process for its conversion into glycolic acid. This process has been tested on a pilot scale for a volume of 10 litres. In later stages of the project, scaling up to 30 litres will be undertaken.
- TPA (terephthalic acid) will be transformed into PCA (protocatechuic acid) through a biotransformation process. This process is being developed with a bacterial strain, and results are not yet available as of the date of preparing this deliverable.
- Lemon peel will be sterilised in a bioreactor, then centrifuged for fermentation, and finally, the solvents will be evaporated to obtain the microbiological oil. This process has been tested on a pilot scale for a volume of 2 litres. In later stages of the project, scaling up to 10-30 litres will be undertaken.

5.4 Demo 3

Figure 24. Relationship Diagram of Demonstrator 3.

In Demonstrator 3, agri-food waste will undergo an enzymatic extraction process, from which a solid phase and a liquid phase will be obtained.

The solid phase will be purified and dehydrated in an oven to produce a dry extract with a high fibre content (Process 2).

For its part, the liquid phase will be concentrated and purified using adsorption resins, and then freeze-dried to obtain an extract enriched in phenolic components (Process 2). Remaining liquid after purification., rich in sugars, will be concentrated and sent to Demonstrator 5 (Process 1).

5.5 Demo 4

Figure 25. Relationship Diagram of Demonstrator 4.

In Demonstrator 4, agri-food waste will undergo an enzymatic extraction process, from which a solid phase and a liquid phase will be derived. The organic phase, rich in sugars, will be concentrated and transferred to Demonstrator 5 (Process 1).

The solid phase will be purified using microwave-assisted extraction, resulting in a residual organic fraction (Process 2), or it will undergo a purification and concentration process to obtain carotenoids, flavonoids, and polyphenols.

The liquid phase will be subjected to centrifugation and ultrafiltration (they may or may not go through this process) and then dehydrated in an oven, thereby obtaining dietary fibre (Process 2). Simultaneously, the flavonoids recovered from ultrafiltration will be incorporated into the purification of the solid phase, where they will be concentrated to obtain the carotenoids, flavonoids, and polyphenols mentioned earlier.

5.6 Demo 5

Figure 26. Relationship Diagram of Demonstrator 5.

In Demonstrator 5, the residues from Demonstrators 2, 3, and 4 will undergo a fermentation process, followed by filtration and drying, with the aim of obtaining PHBV bioplastics and carotenoids (Process 9).

6 Energy analysis of Demonstrators

6.1 Demonstrator 1

Figure 27. Relationship Diagram of Demonstrator 1.

The following describes the energy consumption for each process that comprises Demonstrator 1.

6.1.1 Demonstrator 1. Process 3

Process 3 consists of two stages: pretreatment and optical sorting:

- **Pre-treatment**

This step includes operations such as:

- Shredding: The multilayer material is cut into smaller pieces to facilitate subsequent processing.
- Washing: The material undergoes two washes to remove any contaminants, organic residues, or food particles. To optimise water usage, a recirculation system is implemented. It is worth noting that the washing process is carried out with chilled cold water supplied by chillers, which also serve other equipment in the plant, such as extruders. Washing and extrusion are the processes that demand the most cooling.
- Centrifugation and drying: Moisture is removed from the material through centrifugation and drying to prepare it for the subsequent stages.

The energy consumption in the pretreatment depends on the level of contamination of the plastic to be recycled; however, in the absence of monitoring data, an estimation has been made based on the plant's capacity to process 25 kg/h with a consumption of 60 kW. Thus, to process the target of 1,200 kg, an energy consumption of 2,880 kWh will be required.

- **Optical sorting**

For optical sorting, the electrical consumption is as follows:

- Sensor equipment
- Conveyor motors
- A vibrating table to ensure the proper distribution of the plastic to be recycled

- A lighting module to ensure that the colour of the plastic remains uniform to facilitate the identification of the plastic colour for accurate classification
- A separation module that allows selected plastics to be removed from the conveyor belt
- Cooling system to ensure that the temperature of the electrical components and the computer remains within the appropriate operating range

The total power of these components adds up to 5.5 kW. Considering 48 hours of operation, the energy consumption of this process is 264 kWh.

Table 11. Process summary. Demo 1 (process 3).

Process 3		
PRE-TREATMENT	Raw materials input	
	Bags waste plastics (post- pretreatment only)	1,200.00 kg
	Electricity capacity	60 kW
	Time of operation	48 h
	Energy consumption	
	Electricity	2,880.00 kWh
	Gas oil	27.72 kWh
	Outputs	
	Recycling plastic	1,000.00 kg
	Waste	
OPTICAL SORTING	Raw materials input	1,000 kg
	Electricity capacity	5.5 kW
	Time of operation	48 h
	Energy consumption	264 kWh
	Outputs	
	LDPE multilayers	-
	PET/PE + AI	-
Waste		

6.1.2 Demonstrator 1. Process 4

This process is scheduled to be implemented in November, so no data will be available until then.

6.1.3 Demonstrator 1. Process 5

Process 5 primarily involves the following equipment that consumes energy during the pretreatment necessary to facilitate enzymatic attack in the subsequent two stages of the process: extruder, cutting system, cooling system.

Table 12 summarises the mass and energy balance of the three stages of Process 5 in Demonstrator 1:

Table 12. Process summary. Demo 1 (process 5).

Process 5		
PET/PE pre-treatment (to enhance enzymatic attack)	Raw materials input	
	PET/PE	1.00 kg
	water	0.20 kg
	NaOH	0.00 kg
	Ice cubes	6.00 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Extruder, cutting system, cooling system	6.20 kW
	Time of operation	
	Extruder, cutting system, cooling system	1.00 h
	Energy consumption	
	Extruder, cutting system, cooling system	6.20 kWh
	Outputs	
	Pre treated PET/PE	0.99 kg
Waste		
PET/PE not useful	0.01 kg	
PET PE enzymatic degradation	Raw materials input	1.34 kg
	PET	1.00 kg
	PET Hydrolase	0.00 kg
	Na ₂ HPO ₄	0.14 kg
	NaH ₂ PO ₄	0.19 kg
	Electricity capacity	0.5 kW
	Time of operation	48 h
	Electricity consumption	24 kWh

	Outputs	
	MHET	0.79 kg
	Waste	
	PET with high crystallinity content	0.21 kg
MHET conversion	Raw materials input	1.01 kg
	MHET	1.00 kg
	NaOH	0.00 kg
	Hcl	0.00 kg
	Electricity capacity	0.5 kW
	Time of operation	3 h
	Electricity consumption	1.5 kWh
	Outputs	
	Terephthalic acid TPA	0.79 kg
	Ethylen Glycol EG	0.30 kg
	Waste	
	None	0.00 kg

6.1.4 Demonstrator 1. Total energy consumption and KPI

Table 13 summarises the energy consumption by process:

Table 13. Demonstrator 1. Total energy consumption.

	Energy consumption	
	Thermal	Electricity
Process 3	27.72 kWh	3,144.00 kWh
Process 4	-	-
Process 5	0	31.70 kWh
Total	27.72 kWh	3,175.70 kWh

On the other hand, Table 14 summarises the KPIs of the demo:

Table 14. Demonstrator 1. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/kg)
Terephthalic acid (TPA)	4,054.96
Ethylen Glycol (EG)	10,859.05

6.2 Demonstrator 2

Figure 28. Relationship Diagram of Demonstrator 2.

The following summarises the main energy consumers used in the process of Demonstrator 2 for the treatment of EG and for the yeast fermentation of lemon, with no information available for the analysis of the process for obtaining PCA.

- **Bioreactor**

For the microbial fermentation processes, the BIOSTAT® A bioreactor from Sartorius has been used. To carry out the fermentations, the equipment employs an automatic aeration system that allows for the control of gas supply. For microbial applications, such as yeast fermentation, the system uses air and oxygen to regulate the levels of dissolved oxygen (DO) and pH.

This model of bioreactor provides a continuous flow of air, which is automatically regulated according to the oxygen needs of the microorganism, eliminating the need for manual adjustments of the rotameters. For the trials, the consumption has been regulated to 1 ml/min. Typically, it does not require high pressures, with the standard pressure for air supply being around 1 bar.

The bioreactor used is relatively efficient in terms of gas and energy consumption, as it is designed to reduce cooling water usage and only requires a source of electricity and gas.

The bioreactor, now discontinued, had approximate maximum power output of:

- 200 W for drive
- 200-600 W for heating, depending on the type of vessel (single-wall, double-wall, or single-use)

The consumption of this equipment has been 4.09 kWh over 48 hours, so the average power demand is approximately 85 W.

- **Autoclave.**

It is a vertical autoclave for saturated steam. The model used is the FVA3/A1 from Fedegari, commonly used in analytical and microbiology laboratories. Its function is to sterilise liquids, glassware, textiles, surgical instruments, and high-risk waste. It has a useful capacity of 140 litres (158 litres in total). For sterilisation, the fluid is heated to 148°C, requiring an electric power of 7.5 kW. The time required is 2 hours, so the electrical consumption of this equipment for carrying out sterilisation is estimated at 15 kWh.

- **Cooling bath.**

Cooling baths are used for the preservation of biological samples and chemical reactions. The equipment used in the trials is the FALC SBF -40. This equipment has a cooling capacity that reaches -40°C, being able to maintain this temperature for long periods. For the process, chilled water at 4°C is used. For the cooling cycle, the equipment uses refrigerant R-134a, with an electrical demand of 1.3 kW for heating and 0.52 kW for cooling.

For the calculation of the energy consumption of the cooling bath process, in the absence of energy monitoring measurements, it has been assumed that the water enters at a temperature of 15°C.

$$Q = C_p \cdot m \cdot \Delta T$$

Where:

- Q : the heat extracted from the water, in kWh.
- C_p : the calorific value of water, equivalent to $4.18 \text{ J}/(\text{gK}) = 4.18/3600 \text{ kWh}/(\text{kgC})$
- m : the mass of water, in kg
- ΔT : the temperature change achieved with cooling, in °C or K

To lower this temperature to the 4°C required by the process, the energy expenditure is 0.153 kWh thermal. The available technical data sheets do not provide information on the refrigeration performance or electrical power of the equipment, nor do they provide information on thermal losses. Therefore, a refrigeration performance of ERR 200 is estimated, resulting in an electrical consumption of 0.077 kWh to lower the temperature to 4°C. To account for possible thermal losses, the consumption during the 48 hours of the cooling bath has been considered to be three times that of the initial cooling, resulting in a total estimated consumption of 0.23 kWh.

- **Centrifuge**

The ThermoScientific Megafuge ST4F-R model has been used as a centrifuge. This equipment allows for the separation of components in biological samples. It has a maximum capacity of 4 litres and provides precise temperature control between -10°C and +40°C. It is a high-speed, low-energy consumption centrifuge, electrically operated.

The equipment used allows for the pre-programming of the compressor to start until the temperature reaches the desired level, resulting in energy savings of around 40% compared to other standard equipment. However, the energy consumption of this equipment is

considered negligible at the scale being treated, as the power, although not specified by the manufacturer, is low, and the operating time is also limited (0.33 hours).

- **Stirring plate**

It is a magnetic stirrer model Heidolph 36110519 (HEI-Plate Series). This device is compact and efficient, designed for mixing solutions in laboratories. Like the centrifuge, this equipment also requires an electrical supply, although it has a relatively low energy consumption of 0.8 kW due to the heating element it is equipped with. The energy consumption has been calculated by estimating that the heating element operates for 70% of the time. Thus, the energy consumption during the 24 hours of operation required for the process is estimated to be 13.44 kWh.

- **Rotavapor**

For the trials, the Heidolph HEI-VAP Core model with Vacuubrand MZ 2C NT + AK + EK pump has been used. This rotary evaporator is employed for low-pressure distillation, commonly found in the chemical industry and research laboratories to concentrate solutions. The associated vacuum pump allows for efficient evaporation at low temperatures, reducing the risk of decomposition of sensitive samples. The vacuum pump uses a membrane system to generate vacuum, and the entire setup is electrically powered. The main electrical consumption is due to the heating element, with a power of 1,300 W compared to the maximum demand of 1,400 W for the equipment.

As for the coupled vacuum pump, it has a nominal power of 180 W.

To calculate the energy consumption of the rotary evaporator during its 8 hours of operation, and to estimate the consumption of this equipment without monitoring data, it is assumed that the heating element operates at maximum capacity for 70% of the time and that the vacuum pump runs at 100% during the 8 hours. Thus, an energy consumption of 9.28 kWh is obtained.

- **Air compressor**

For the trials, the compressed air line from UNIMIB University has been used. To calculate the energy consumption of the compressor, the following formula has been used: [39]

$$P = \frac{Q \cdot (P_2 - P_1)}{60 \cdot \eta}$$

Where:

- P is the power of the compressor in kW.
- Q is the air flow rate in litres per minute, in L/min (1 l/min).
- P₂ is the outlet pressure, in kPa (2 bar = 200 kPa).
- P₁ is the atmospheric pressure, in kPa (1 bar = 100 kPa).
- η is the efficiency of the compressor (a typical value is 0.7 - 0.8; for this case, it is estimated to be 0.7).

Thus, with the above data, an energy consumption of 2.38 kWh is calculated.

6.2.1 Demonstrator 2. EG to biomass and glycolic acid

The process for obtaining glycolic acid and biomass from the EG originating from Demo 1 is illustrated in Figure 29 :

Figure 29. Demonstrator 2. EG to biomass and glycolic acid.

The following table presents the energy balances for each of the processes in this line of Demo 2.

Table 15. Process summary. Demo 2 (EG to biomass and glycolic acid).

Process 8 (Input: EG)		
Biomass and GA production	Raw materials input	
	EG from demo 1	3 L
	Glucose monohydrate	330 L
	Yeast Extract	130 L
	Tryptone	260 L
	Polypropylene Glycol	0,031 L
	Demineralized H2O	8 L
	KOH	124 g
	HCl	0,008 L
	Compressed air	133.920 L
	Cooling water	12 L
	Electricity capacity	1 kW
	Stirred tank reactor	0,15 kW
	Cooling bath	1,30 kW
	Time of operation	144 h
Stirred tank reactor	144 h	
Cooling bath	144 h	

	Energy consumption	14 kWh
	Stirred tank reactor	13,45 kWh
	Cooling bath	0,153 kWh
	Air compressor	37 kWh
	Outputs (Fermentation broth (cells + GA))	8.500,0 l
	Waste	-
DWP: centrifugation	Raw materials input	
	Fermentation broth	8.500,0
	Sterile Disposable Bottle Top Filters with PES Membrane (0.22 µm)	1
	Electricity capacity	
	Tangential flow filtration	0,217 kW
	Time of operation	12 h
	Tangential flow filtration	12 h
	Filtration	0,02 h
	Energy consumption	
	Tangential flow filtration	2,6 kWh
	Outputs	
	Glycolic Acid 24 g/L (aqueous solution)	8,000 L
	Biomass	0,500 L
	Waste	-

6.2.2 Demonstrator 2. Total energy consumption and KPI (EG to biomass and GA)

The total energy consumption of this process is 16.20 kWh for a scale of 10 litres; per product, it would be:

Table 16. Demonstrator 2. EG to biomass and Glycolic Acid. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/l)
Glycolic Acid (8l)	2.03

Biomass (0.5l)	32.41
Total output volume (8.5l)	1.91

6.2.3 Demonstrator 2. Lemmon to microbial oil

The process for obtaining microbial oil from the lemon in Demonstrator 2 is shown in Figure 30:

Figure 30. Demonstrator 2. Lemmon to microbial oil.

The following summarises the consumption for a pilot scale of 2 litres:

Table 17. Process summary. Demo 2 (yeast fermentation line).

Process 8 (Input: lemon)		
Yeast Fermentation	Raw materials input	
	Lemon Extract (from Demo 3)	0.8 L
	Polypropylene Glycol	0.001 L
	Demineralized H2O	0.2 L
	KOH	0.5 g
	HCl	0.525 mL
	Compressed air	2880 L
	Cooling water	12 L
	Electricity capacity	9 kW
	Autoclave	7.50 kW
	Stirred tank reactor	0.09 kW
	Cooling bath	1.30 kW
	Time of operation	48 h
	Autoclave	2 h
	Stirred tank reactor	48 h
	Cooling bath	48 h
	Energy consumption	22 kWh

	Autoclave	15.00 kWh
	Stirred tank reactor	4.09 kWh
	Cooling bath	0.230 kWh
	Air compressor	2.38 kWh
	Outputs (Fermentation broth (cells + spent medium))	0.915 l
	Waste	0 kg
DWP: centrifugation	Raw materials input	
	Fermentation broth	0.915 L
	Electricity capacity	
	Centrifuge	0.00 kW
	Time of operation	
	Centrifuge	0.33 h
	Energy consumption	
	Centrifuge	0.00 kWh
	Outputs	
	Spent medium	0.860 L
Cell slurry	0.055 L	
DWP: extraction	Raw materials input	
	Cell slurry	0.055 L
	Solvent BA	0.500 L
	Solvent K1	1.000 L
	Electricity capacity	
	Stirring plate	0.80 kW
	Time of operation	
	Stirring plate	24.00 h
	Energy consumption	
	Stirring plate	13.44 kWh
	Outputs	
	Organic phase (containing the oil)	
	Waste	

Solvent evaporation	Acqueous phase	0.655 L
	Raw materials input	
	Organic phase (containing the oil)	0.9 L
	Electricity capacity	
	Rotavapor	1.40 kW
	Vacuum pump	0.18 kW
	Time of operation	
	Rotavapor + vacuum pump	8.00 h
	Energy consumption	
	Rotavapor + vacuum pump	9.28 kWh
	Outputs	
	Microbial oil	11.79 g
	Waste	
	Solvent mix BA/K1 (emissions to air)	0.900 L

6.2.4 Demonstrator 2. Total energy consumption and KPI (lemon to microbial oil)

The total energy consumption of this process is 44.42 kWh for a scale of 10 litres, which would produce 11.79 g of microbial oil. The energy consumption KPI would be 3.77 kWh/g.

Table 18. Demonstrator 2. EG to biomass and Glycolic Acid. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/l)
Microbial oil	3.77

6.3 Demonstrator 3

In these demonstrators, CTNC has implemented the green extraction + ultrasound-assisted extraction pilot plant to extract dietary fibres, phenolic compounds & carotenoids (100 kg/h), including preliminary conditioning, and purification and conservation after the extraction processes (15 kg). DMC has implemented the green extraction + enzymatic hydrolysis assisted extraction+ microwave-assisted extraction (50 kg/h) pilot plant to obtain high solubility fibres, phenolic substances & carotenoids, including preliminary conditioning, and purification and conservation after the extraction processes (25kg).

Demonstrator 3 has been installed in CTNC's facilities. The process aims to obtain products that can be used on food, nutraceutical and cosmetic formulations. To do so, organic residues and subproducts are pretreated by washing and cutting them if required. After this

initial stage, an extraction operation is applied to these substances. At pilot scale, both enzymatic and ultrasound assisted extractions have been tested. As a result of the extraction, two different phases are obtained, a solid and a liquid one.

Solid phase is purified, finally stabilizing it through dehydration in an oven. In this way, a dehydrated extract with high content of fibre is obtained.

Liquid phase is treated in a concentration/filtration process and then submitted to an adsorption and desorption treatment with resins. Then, this phase is stabilized through lyophilization (atomization was discarded). Finally, a freeze-dried extract rich in phenolic compounds is obtained.

Consumption in Demonstrator 3 (process 1) is due to the resistors for heating the solutions and the agitators for mixing them.

Figure 31. Demonstrator 3. High added value substances from agri-food waste by green extraction + ultrasound

As part of demonstrator 3, there is a set of equipment that needs to be used. This involves a vacuum reactor for enzymatic extraction, an oven to dehydrate the purified solid phase, a filtration station and resins treatment in which the liquid extract is concentrated and a lyophilization machine to freeze-dry the liquid extract.

The following is a detailed analysis of each energy-consuming equipment:

- **Cutter**

In the pre-treatment stage, the energy consumption arises from the cutting process of the raw material. The power of the cutting machine is 3 kW, and it operates continuously for about 20 minutes. Therefore, the energy consumption of this equipment during the process is 1 kWh.

- **Decanter**

For the filtration process, a decanter is used, which is equipped with a 10.3 kW motor. This motor operates for 10 minutes, resulting in an energy consumption of 1 kWh.

- **Mixing tank**

For the enzymatic extraction process, a mixing tank is used that operates with natural gas. It is known that the consumption of the tank is 6 m³/h, and it operates for a duration of 1 hour and 25 minutes, resulting in a total natural gas consumption of 8.5 m³.

To calculate the energy associated with that volume of natural gas, it is necessary to consider that the conversion factor for natural gas can vary depending on its quality and energy content. According to the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) guidelines, a commonly used value for 1 m³ of natural gas ranges from 9.69 to 11.68 kWh. For the calculation, a Inferior Calorific Power (ICP) of natural gas of 10.83 kWh/m³ has been used, which is one of the most commonly used by gas supply companies in Spain. Thus, an energy consumption of 92.06 kWh is obtained.

- **Concentrator**

For the concentration phase, a membrane filtration equipment with a power of 36 kW is used. This process lasts for one hour, resulting in an energy consumption of 36 kWh due to the concentration process.

- **Adsorption equipment**

For the purification process, an adsorption and desorption equipment using resins (1–2 kg of adsorption resins) is employed. The adsorption phase lasts for 3 hours and requires a power of 0.25 kW. Meanwhile, the desorption phase lasts for 1 hour and demands a power of 0.37 kW. Therefore, the total energy consumption of this equipment is 1.12 kWh (0.75 kWh during adsorption and 0.37 kWh during desorption).

- **Oven**

For the dehydration process, a small oven with a power of 0.8 kW is used for 48 hours, resulting in a consumption of 38.40 kWh. This process yields 3.6 kg of fibre extract, with the remainder (36.4 kg) being evaporated water.

- **Lyophilisation**

Lyophilisation is a process in which a completely frozen sample is placed under vacuum to remove water or other solvents from the sample, allowing the ice to change directly from solid to vapour without passing through a liquid phase. For this process, a machine with a power of 2.5 kW is used, and the process lasts for 96 hours. The total consumption for this phase is 240 kWh, yielding 0.6 kg of phenolic extract, with the remainder (79.40 kg) being evaporated water.

The following summarises the energy consumption calculated for each process.

6.3.1 Demonstrator 3. Process 1

Figure 32. Demonstrator 3, process 1.

The process comprises three stages:

1. Pre-treatment

- Inputs: 50 kg of agri-food waste processed.
- Outputs: no waste generated; all material processed remains intact.
- Energy: 1 kWh.

2. Enzymatic extraction and filtration

- Inputs: 0.15 m³ of water, 50 kg of agri-food waste and 0.005 kg of enzyme. An additional 0.19 m³ of water was used for the boiler.
- Outputs: 190 kg of water evaporated; no residual waste.
- Energy: 93.06 kWh (92.06 kWh from natural gas and 1 kWh electricity).

3. Purification

- Inputs: 200 kg of solid-liquid mixture after extraction and 1.5 kg of resins.
- Outputs: 0.08 m³ of condensed water; no additional waste.
- Energy: 37.12 kWh.

6.3.2 Demonstrator 3. Process 2

Figure 33. Demonstrator 3, process 2.

The process consists of two stages:

1. Dehydration

- Inputs: 40 kg of agri-food waste.
- Outputs: 3.6 kg of dehydrated fibre and 36.4 kg of evaporated water.
- Energy: 38.4 kWh.

2. Stabilisation (Lyophilisation)

- Inputs: 80 kg of agri-food waste.
- Outputs: 0.6 kg of dehydrated liquid extract and 79.4 kg of evaporated water.

- Energy: 240 kWh.

6.3.3 Demonstrator 3. Total energy consumption and KPI

The total energy consumption calculated for this demonstrator, taking into account the energy consumption of the solid phase and the liquid phase processes, is 409.58 kWh.

Table 19. Demonstrator 3. Total energy consumption.

	Process 1	Process 2	
		Solid phase	Liquid phase
Electricity	39.12 kWh	38.40 kWh	240.00 kWh
Natural gas	92.06 kWh	0.00 kWh	0.00 kWh

For a scale of 50 kg, the energy consumption ratios per kg of output are shown in Table 20:

Table 20. Demonstrator 3. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/kg)
Fibre extract (169.58 kWh)	47.10
Phenolic extract (371.18 kWh)	618.63

6.4 Demonstrator 4

This demonstrator consists of two processes. The first is for obtaining the organic waste to be processed in demonstrator 5. The second is for the treatment of the remaining solid and liquid phases.

The following describes the energy-consuming equipment associated with the processes:

- **Industrial cutter**

In the pre-treatment, the artichoke waste is chopped for subsequent processing. The industrial cutting machine has an electrical capacity of 3.4 kW. This equipment is used for 5 minutes to process 100 kg of artichoke, resulting in an energy consumption of 0.28 kWh for the cutting process.

- **Microwave**

Both for the enzymatic extraction and for the microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), the industrial microwave equipment produced by SAIREM specifically for the project is used. This industrial microwave has a power of 6 kW.

For the enzymatic extraction, this equipment is used for 30 minutes to process 100 kg of artichoke, resulting in a total energy consumption of 3 kWh.

On the other hand, for the MAE, the equipment is used 10 times in 40-minute intervals, leading to an energy consumption of 40 kWh (4 kWh per batch).

Figure 34. Microwave extractor EMU06.

- **Centrifugation**

To separate the solid phase from the liquid phase, a centrifuge model Comicondor TMS-IV 1000 – 500 is used. This equipment has an electrical power of 20 kW. For the process, it operates for 1 hour, resulting in an energy consumption of 20 kWh.

Figure 35. Centrifuge Comicondor TMS-IV 1000 – 500.

- **Vacuum destillator**

This equipment is used during the purification and concentration process. It has a power rating of 0.15 kW and is operated for 10 hours, resulting in an energy consumption of 1.5 kWh.

- **Freeze-dryer**

This equipment is also used during the purification and concentration process. It has a power rating of 0.04 kW and is operated for 24 hours, resulting in an energy consumption of 0.96 kWh.

- **Ultrafiltration equipment**

For ultrafiltration, the M500UF equipment from Bionet is used. This equipment has an electrical power rating of 7.5 kW and operates for 1 hour, resulting in an energy consumption of 7.5 kWh for the ultrafiltration process.

- **Dehydration**

For dehydration, an oven is used to process 30 kg of a dietary fibresolution, extracting 1.2 kg of solid enriched in dietary fibres through heating. The energy consumption for this process is 48 kWh.

The oven's operating time varies based on the water content in the fibre extract, ranging from 10 to 24 hours.

6.4.1 Demonstrator 4. Process 1

In the following table, the balance for Process 1 within Demonstrator 4 is presented:

Table 21. Process summary. Demo 4. Process 1.

Process 1		
Pre-treatment	Raw materials input	
	Artichoke waste	100 kg
	Water	205 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Industrial cutter (MAINCA CM-22)	3.4 kW
	Time of operation	
	Industrial cutter	0.08 h
	Energy consumption	
	Industrial cutter	0.28 kWh
	Outputs	
	Washed and cutted artichoke	100 kg
Waste		
None	0.0 kg	
Enzimatic extraction	Raw materials input	
	Washed artichoke	100 kg
	Water	300 kg
	Enzymes	10 ml
	Citric acid	0,1 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Microwave extractor EMU06	6.0 kW

	Time of operation	
	Microwave extractor EMU06	0.5 h
	Energy consumption	
	Microwave extractor EMU06	3.00 kWh
	Outputs	
	Solid phase (antioxidants)	100 kg
	Liquid phase (dietary fibres)	300.11 kg
	Waste	
None	0.0 kg	
Centrifugation (could be omitted)	Raw materials input	
	Liquid phase (dietary fibres)	300 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Centrifuge (Comicondor TMS-IV 1000 - 500)	20 kW
	Time of operation	
	Centrifuge (Comicondor TMS-IV 1000 - 500)	1.00 h
	Energy consumption	
	Centrifuge (Comicondor TMS-IV 1000 - 500)	20kWh
	Outputs	
	liquid phase II (dietary fibres)	300 kg
	Solid	Negligible
	Waste	
None	0.0 kg	

6.4.2 Demonstrator 4. Process 2 (solid phase)

Table 22 presents the energy summary of the solid phase of Process 2 within Demonstrator 4:

Table 22. Process summary. Demo 4. Process 2 (solid phase).

	Process 2 (solid phase)	
Microwave extraction (MAE) - To be repeated 10 times to process the 100kg of solid	Raw materials input	
	Solid phase (antioxidants)	10 kg
	Water	40 kg

	Ethanol	60 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Microwave extractor EMU06 (used only 5 kW from the 6 kW)	5.0 kW
	Time of operation	
	Microwave extractor EMU06	0.67 h
	Energy consumption	
	Microwave extractor EMU06	3.33 kWh
	Outputs	
	Solution of antioxidants	100 kg
	Waste	
	Solid	10.0 kg
Purification + Concentration	Raw materials input	
	Solution of Antioxidants	100 kg
	EtOH	5 kg
	Resin (HP20)	0,2 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Vacuum distillator	0,15 kW
	Freeze-dryer	0,04 kW
	Time of operation	
	Vacuum distillator	10 h
	Freeze-dryer	24 h
	Energy consumption	
	Vacuum distillator	1,5 kWh
	Freeze-dryer	1 kWh
	Outputs	
	Antioxidant extract	0,03 kg
Resin (HP20)	0,2 kg	

	EtOH	5 kg
	Waste	
	Water	60.0 kg

6.4.3 Demonstrator 4. Process 2 (liquid phase)

Table 23 presents the energy summary of the liquid phase of Process 2 within Demonstrator 4:

Table 23. Process summary. Demo 2 (liquid phase).

Process 2 (liquid phase)		
Ultrafiltration	Raw materials input	
	liquid phase II (dietary fibers)	300 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	M500UF - Bionet	7.5 kW
	Time of operation	
	M500UF - Bionet	1 h
	Energy consumption	
	M500UF - Bionet	7.5 kWh
	Outputs	
	Solution of dietary fibres	30 kg
	Waste	
	Solid	Unknown
Dehydration	Raw materials input	
	Solution of dietary fibres	30 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Oven	4.8 kW (app.)
	Time of operation	
	Oven	10 - 48 h
	Energy consumption	
	Oven	48 kWh
Outputs		

Waste	Solid enriched in dietary fibers	1.2 kg
	Water vapour	28.8 kg
	Waste	
	Solid	Unknown

6.4.4 Demonstrator 4. Total energy consumption and KPI

The total energy consumption calculated for this demonstrator, considering the energy consumption of both the solid phase and liquid phase processes, is 85.28 kWh.

Table 24. Demonstrator 4. Total energy consumption.

	Energy consumption (kWh)
Process 1	23.28
Process 2	61.33
Solid phase	5.83
Liquid phase	55.5

Table 25 summarises the KPIs of demonstrator 4 for a scale of 100 kg:

Table 25. Demonstrator 4. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/kg)
Solution of antioxidants	0.29
Antioxidant extract	2,626.11
Resin (HP20)	393.92
EtOH	15.76

6.5 Demonstrator 5

Demonstrator 5 corresponds to process 9 of the project. For laboratory-scale testing, lemon, apple, and grape waste (from demonstrator 3) has been used as a carbon source, conducting processes including fermentation, filtration, drying, PHBV extraction and purification, and carotenoid extraction.

It is noteworthy that for the tests, the liquid phase of the lemon waste from demonstrator 3, obtained after the extraction process and subsequent phase separation through sieving filtration, has been used. Therefore, the energy consumption for obtaining this waste should also be taken into account. To separate the consumptions of demonstrators 3 and 5, both

calculations have been made for energy consumption and KPIs (including and excluding these values).

The following describes the equipment used in Demonstrator 5:

- **Orbital shaker**

The orbital shaker has been used to mix, homogenise, and agitate samples. As an energy-consuming element, orbital shakers feature a motorised arm that moves the container in an orbital pattern, allowing for thorough mixing of the solution.

This equipment has a small motor with a power rating of 450 W. For the process, this equipment was used continuously for 24 hours, resulting in an energy consumption of 10.8 kWh.

- **Bioreactors**

In the fermentation process, two bioreactors of different capacities have been used: one with a capacity of 30 litres and a power rating of 4 kW, and another with a capacity of 300 litres and a power rating of 1.12 kW. These bioreactors were operated for 48 and 96 hours, respectively. Consequently, the energy consumption from the bioreactors was 192.00 kWh and 107.52 kWh.

- **Air compressor**

The fermentation processes in the bioreactors require a supply of compressed air for oxygenation and to agitate the mixture, ensuring efficient distribution of nutrients and gases.

For the 30-litre bioreactor, a 3 kW air compressor was used, which operated continuously for the 48 hours of the process. Consequently, the energy consumption of this compressor was 144 kWh.

On the other hand, the 300-litre bioreactor required a 0.75 kW compressor running for the 96 hours of the process. The energy consumption of this compressor amounted to 72 kWh.

- **Heat supplier**

In order to maintain and control the temperature in the bioreactor at an optimal level for promoting the growth of microorganisms, a heater is used. This heater operates for an effective time of 8 hours, with a total consumption of 128 kWh and an average power usage of 16 kW.

- **Tangential filtration unit**

For the separation and concentration of the mixture, a Tangential Flow Filtration (TFF) unit has been used. Unlike traditional filtration, where the flow is perpendicular to the membrane, in tangential filtration, the fluid flows parallel to the surface of the filter. This configuration reduces obstruction and enables more efficient and continuous processes.

For the process, a TFF unit with a power rating of 1.5 kW was operated for 24 hours, resulting in a consumption of 36 kWh for the production of concentrated biomass.

- **Drying oven**

The concentrated biomass sample is dried in an oven for 48 hours, resulting in a consumption of 129.6 kWh, with an average power of 2.7 kW.

• **PHBV extraction and purification equipment**

For the extraction and purification of PHBV from the biomass, the equipment shown in Figure 36, extracted from deliverable D5.3, has been used. The main energy consumers of this equipment include the motor stirrer, the heating jacket, the oil system, the solvent condenser, and the temperature control unit.

Figure 36. Equipment used for the PHBV purification and extraction.

From these components, the following power ratings and consumptions are estimated:

- Motor Stirrer: 0.5 kW for 90 minutes, resulting in a consumption of 0.8 kWh.
- Heating Jacket and Heated Oil Unit: 3 kW for 90 minutes, resulting in a consumption of 4.5 kWh.
- Inline Solvent Vapor Condenser Unit: 1 kW for 90 minutes, resulting in a consumption of 1.5 kWh.
- Temperature Control Unit: 1 kW for 90 minutes, resulting in a consumption of 1.5 kWh.

6.5.1 Demonstrator 5. Fermentation, filtration and drying

The following table summarises the mass and energy balance of the fermentation, filtration, and drying processes:

Table 26. Process summary. Demo 5. Mass and energy balances in the general line.

Process 9 (fermentation, filtration and drying)	
Fermentation	Raw materials input
	Salts 48.02 kg

Nitrogen source	1.61 kg
Carbon source	2.10 kg
Phosphorous source	21 g
NaOH	400 g
HCl	1.00 kg
Electricity capacity	25 kW
Orbital shaker	0.45 kW
30 L bioreactor	4.00 kW
Air compressor	3.00 kW
300 L bioreactor	1.12 kW
Heat supplier	16.00 kW
Air supplier	0.75 kW
Time of operation	96 h
Orbital shaker	24 h
30 L bioreactor	48 h
Air compressor	48 h
300 L bioreactor	96 h
Heat supplier	8 h
Air supplier	96 h
Energy consumption	203 kWh
Orbital shaker	10.80 kWh
30 L bioreactor	192.00 kWh
Air compressor	144.00 kWh
300 L bioreactor	107.52 kWh
Heat supplier	128.00 kWh
Air supplier	72 kWh
Outputs (Fermentation broth (cells + spent medium))	
Fermentation culture	200.0 L
Waste	
Wash water	200.0 L

Filtration	Raw materials input	
	Fermentation culture	200.0 L
	Electricity capacity	
	Tangential filtration unit	1.5 kW
	Time of operation	
	Tangential filtration unit	24 h
	Energy consumption	
	Tangential filtration unit	36.0 kWh
	Outputs	
	Concentrated biomass	15 l
	Water brine	185 l
	Waste	
	Wash water	50.0 l
Drying	Raw materials input	
	Concentrated biomass	15.0 L
	Electricity capacity	
	Drying oven	2.7 kW
	Time of operation	
	Drying oven	48 h
	Energy consumption	
	Drying oven	129.6 kWh
	Outputs	
	Dried biomass	2 kg
	Waste	
None		

6.5.2 Demonstrator 5. PHBV extraction and purification

Table 27 summarises the energy consumption of the PHBV extraction and purification process:

Table 27. Process summary. Demo 5. Mass and energy balances in PHBV extraction and purification.

Process 9	
PHBV extraction and purification	Raw materials input
	Biomass 13.0 kg
	Electricity capacity
	Motor Stirrer 0.5 kW
	Heating jacket and heated oil unit 3.0 kW
	Inline solvent vapor condenser unit 1.0 kW
	Temperature control unit 1.0 kW
	Time of operation
	Motor Stirrer 1.5 h
	Heating jacket and heated oil unit 1.5 h
	Inline solvent vapor condenser unit 1.5 h
	Temperature control unit 1.5 h
	Energy consumption 8 kWh
	Motor Stirrer 0.8 kWh
	Heating jacket and heated oil unit 4.5 kWh
	Inline solvent vapor condenser unit 1.5 kWh
	Temperature control unit 1.5 kWh
	Outputs
	PHBV 500 g
	Water brine -
Waste	
- -	

6.5.3 Demonstrator 5. Total energy consumption and KPI

Table 28 summarises the energy consumption in each process line and the total.

Table 28. Demonstrator 5. Total energy consumption.

	Energy consumption (kWh)
Liquid lemon extract (from Demonstrator 3)	131.2 kWh
Fermentation-Filtration-Drying	203 kWh
PHBV extraction and purification	8 kWh
Total	211 kWh

Table 29 summarises the KPIs of demonstrator 5 for the production of 500g of PHBV:

Table 29. Demonstrator 5. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/kg)
PHBV (excluding consumption for obtaining lemon liquid)	422.10
PHBV (including consumption for obtaining lemon liquid)	684.45

6.6 Demonstrators 6 + 8

Within the framework of demonstrators 6 and 8, an extrusion and compounding installation has been built, consisting of a feed hopper and an extruder with auxiliary components such as motors for transportation and mixing, air compressors, and heating systems for melting the polymers.

The installation can handle an input flow of 648 kg/h to produce 625 kg/h of pellets. The electrical power of the demonstrator is 280 kW.

To achieve the project's production target of 500 kg, an operating time of 48 minutes is required. Considering this, the necessary electrical consumption to obtain the 500 kg is 224.0 kWh.

Table 30 summarises the estimated energy balance of these demonstrators:

Table 30. Process summary. Demonstrators 6+8.

	Demos 6 + 8	
General process	Raw materials input	518 kg
	Electricity capacity	280 kW
	Time of operation	0.8 h
	Energy consumption	224 kWh

	Outputs	500 kg
	Waste	-

6.6.1 Demonstrator 6+8. Total energy consumption and KPI

The energy consumption of this demonstrator is estimated at 224 kWh for the production of 500 kg. For this same scale, the project's KPI is 0.448 kWh/kg.

Table 31. Demonstrators 6+8. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/kg)
Biodegradable pellet for food packaging (DEMO 6) and agricultural film (DEMO 8)	0.448

6.7 Demonstrators 7, 9

Demonstrators 7 and 9 begin with multilayer treatment through decontamination using the Erema vacuum reactor. For this reason, they are considered together, although the remaining processes differ slightly between the two demonstrators, as Demonstrator 9 incorporates modified aluminium and recycled agricultural mulching into the process.

The structure of the processes in both demonstrators is as follows:

- **Multilayer Treatment for Decontamination of LDPE:** In the “Multilayer Treatment” process, decontamination of the polyethylene (PE) is carried out to remove impurities, gases, and contaminants present in the layers of the multilayer materials.
- **Extrusion and Compatibilization:** Extrusion is performed to promote a uniform dispersion of polymers, improving the quality of the final material. Compatibilization is carried out to ensure that the polymers can mix homogeneously, which requires the use of compatibilizers.
- **Transformation (Conventional Compounds):** The recycled material undergoes blown extrusion and cast extrusion processes to shape products or more complex structures. The first extrusion process (blown extrusion) is used to create thin plastic films, such as those used in wraps or bags, while the second (cast extrusion) is used to create thicker films or produce films with a uniform quality.

Analysing the Erema Vacuum Reactor, Common to Both Demonstrators:

- **Erema vacuum reactor**

The use of vacuum in the decontamination process ensures the effective extraction of volatile contaminants, guaranteeing that the material is pure enough to be recycled in subsequent stages.

To achieve this, the Erema vacuum reactor is employed to treat PET. This technology has proven to be up to 36% more energy-efficient than other technologies in terms of energy consumption, thanks to its compact design and optimised use of vacuum and inline

crystallisation. The consumption of this reactor is calculated at 0.35 kWh/kg, including the expected power consumption of the necessary water chillers at the customer's facility.

Next, the remaining processes will be analysed.

6.7.1 Demonstrator 7

Figure 37. General scheme of demonstrator 7

- **Extrusion and compatibilization**

After decontamination, extrusion takes place at GWC facilities, processing 520.6 kg of plastic bags to obtain 500 kg of recycled plastic. To enhance the mixing process, 10.4 kg of compatibiliser is used. Along with the 500 kg of recycled plastic, 31 kg of filter chunk is produced.

The energy consumption of this process is estimated at 380 kWh.

- **Transformation (blown extrusion and cast extrusion)**

In demonstrator 7, a PE extrusion process is carried out. The current tested values indicate a power demand of 380 kW to handle an input flow of 833 kg/h. Thus, the proportional consumption to obtain 500 kg will be 237.5 kWh.

The compatibilisation of polyethylene (PE) refers to the process of enhancing the interaction between PE and other polymers in blends or compounds, as polyethylene alone tends to be chemically inert and does not mix well with other materials due to its low polarity.

Table 32. Process summary. Demo 7.

		DEMO 7	
Multilayer treatment	Raw materials input		
	LDPE multilayers		-
	Electricity capacity		
	Erema vacuum reactor		-
	Time of operation		
	Erema vacuum reactor		-
	Energy consumption		
Erema vacuum reactor			182.2 kWh

	Outputs	
	bags waste plastics (post- pretreatment, sorting and delamination)	520.6 kg
	Waste	
	-	-
Extrusion + compatibilization (Demo 7)	Raw materials input	
	bags waste plastics (post- pretreatment, sorting and delamination)	520.6 kg
	Compatibilizer	10.4 kg
	Electricity capacity	
	Extrusion	380.0 kW
	Time of operation	
	Extrusion	1.0 h
	Energy consumption	380.0 kWh
	Extrusion	380.0 kWh
	Outputs	
	Recycling plastic	500 kg
	Filter chunk	31 kg
	Waste	
	-	
Transformation	Extrusion speed	5 kg/h
	Raw materials input	1,000 kg
	LDPE	680 kg
	EVOH	80 kg
	PA	180 kg
	COMPATIBILIZER	40 kg
	AI	20 kg
	Electricity capacity	6.99 kW
	Extruder	4.70 kW
	Feeding	0.24 kW
	Cutting	1.05 kW

Heater (for extruder)	1.00 kW
Time of operation	200 h
Extruder (200hx70%)	200 h
Feeding (200hx70%)	200 h
Cutting (200hx70%)	200 h
Heater (for extruder) (27.5h)	27.5 h
Energy consumption	1,226 kWh
Extruder	940 kWh
Feeding	48 kWh
Cutting	210 kWh
Heater (for extruder)	28 kWh
Outputs	
Pellets	1,000 kg
Film	1,000 kg
Waste	
None	0.00 kg

6.7.2 Demonstrator 7. Total energy consumption and KPI

The following tables summarise the energy consumption and KPIs of demonstrator 7 for the production of 500 kg of product, pending the determination of the remaining consumptions:

Table 33. Demonstrator 7. Total energy consumption.

	Consumption (kWh)
Multilayer treatment	182.21
Extrusion + compatibilization (Demo 7)	380.00
Transformation	1,225.50
Total	1,787.71

Table 34. Demonstrator 7. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/kg)
Pellets	0.559
Film	0.559

6.7.3 Demonstrator 9

Figure 38. General scheme of demonstrator 9

Demonstrator 9 includes the following energy consumers:

- **Grinder, drying silo and flake storage silo:**

There are two grinder units with a flake grinding mesh of Ø25 for grinding recycled agricultural mulching, a drying silo to reduce the moisture content of the flakes below 5%, and a silo for storage of the flakes.

The consumption of this line, including grinders, conveyor motors, etc., is 360 kW. To achieve 500 kg of agricultural mulching flakes at the output of the extrusion (the next process), the line needs to operate for approximately 37 minutes, as it can process 1,400 kg/h of material, generating an output of 833 kg/h. Thus, the estimated consumption of this line will be 225.0 kWh, with an input of 875 kg and an output of 520.63 kg of agricultural mulching.

- **Extruder and final product mixing Silo**

The material from the previous line is fed into an extruder, and the output is directed to a silo.

The power of the extruder, including the auxiliary elements (motors) of the line, is 375 kW, with a capacity to process agricultural mulching of 833 kg/h to obtain 800 kg/h. Operating the line for 37.5 minutes, the consumption will be 234.4 kWh to produce 500 kg at the output of the process.

Figure 39 summarises the flows for a 37.5-minute operation time of these last two processes.

Figure 39. Grinding and extruding processes' description.

Finally, a decontamination process is carried out; however, at this stage of the project, there is still insufficient information to conduct the energy analysis of this process.

Table 35. Process summary. Demo 9.

		Demo 9
Process	Raw materials input	875 kg
	Electricity capacity	735.0 kW
	Time of operation	0.63 h
	Energy consumption	459.4 kWh
	Outputs	500 kg
	Waste	Unknown

6.7.4 Demonstrator 9. Total energy consumption and KPI

Table 36 summarises the KPIs for demonstrator 9 for the production of 500 kg of product, pending the determination of the remaining consumptions.

Table 36. Demonstrator 9. KPIs.

	KPI (kWh/kg)
Erema vacuum reactor	0.35
Grinder + dryer + extrusion	0.919
Decontamination	Unknown
Total	> 1.269

7 Summary of KPIs

The following table provides a summary of KPIs related to the energy consumption associated with the production of various products across the different demonstrators in the Agro2Circular project. These KPIs, expressed in kWh per kilogram or litre, serve as essential metrics for evaluating the efficiency of each process in terms of energy usage. By examining these values, it is possible to identify which processes or products have higher energy demands and thereby establish opportunities for improving energy efficiency. The results presented in this table highlight the current energy consumption levels required for producing each product, offering valuable insights for further optimisation efforts and enhancing the sustainability of these processes as they scale.

Table 37. Summary of KPIs.

	Product	KPI	Unit
Demo 1	EG	4,054.96	kWh/kg
	TPA	10,859.05	kWh/kg
Demo 2	Glycolic acid 24 g/L	2.03	kWh/l
	Biomass	32.41	kWh/l
	Microbial oil	3.77	kWh/l
Demo 3	Dehydrated extract with high fiber content	47.10	kWh/kg
	Freeze-dried extract rich in phenolic compounds	618.63	kWh/kg
Demo 4	Solution of antioxidants	0.29	kWh/kg
	Antioxidant extract	2,626.11	kWh/kg
	Resin (HP20)	393.92	kWh/kg
	EtOH	15.76	kWh/kg
Demo 5	PHBV (excluding consumption for obtaining lemon liquid)	422.10	kWh/kg
	PHBV (including consumption for obtaining lemon liquid)	684.45	kWh/kg
Demo 6	Biodegradable pellet for food packaging	0.448	kWh/kg
Demo 7	Recyclable conventional pellet for food packaging	0.559	kWh/kg
Demo 8	Agricultural film	0.448	kWh/kg
Demo 9	Recyclable conventional pellet for agricultural applications	1.27	kWh/kg

8 Energy Efficiency Recommendations for the Operation of Demos Sites

The analysis of the energy consumptions of the demonstrators has led to several conclusions and recommendations for improving the energy efficiency of the processes. Below, we summarise those with the greatest potential for efficiency improvement.

8.1 Heat recovery from steams

In some demonstrators, such as Demonstrator 4, a significant amount of water vapour has been observed.

To estimate the recoverable energy from this vapour, it has been assumed that the vapour temperature is 100 °C and the pressure is 1 atmosphere. Under this assumption, the latent heat of vaporisation of water is 2,260 kJ/kg, which is equivalent to approximately 0.628 kWh/kg.

In an industrial plant, this energy can be harnessed for recovery through heat exchangers at other points in the facility where there is a demand for heat. If there is no heat demand at any point in the plant but there is a demand for cooling, an absorption machine can be installed. These machines utilise the heat absorbed during the evaporation process of a fluid to produce cold. In this way, they are capable of generating cold from heat.

Figure 40. Operation of an absorption machine [40]

8.2 Adopt high energy efficiency technologies for heating

Most of the demonstrators analysed, when conducting small-scale tests, many of which take place in laboratories, use electric ovens as a source of heat. However, this is not the most efficient technology, exhibiting one of the lowest efficiencies among the available options.

In terms of scaling up, it is recommended to use alternative technologies such as:

- **Air heaters.** These are advisable when the required temperatures are not excessively high, that is, below 90°C. Air heaters are devices that work by heating air, which is then used to warm the environment or a process. They are particularly useful in situations where a uniform and constant heat is required. Their efficiency lies in the fact that they can better utilise electrical energy than traditional electric ovens, and in some cases, allow for the recovery of residual heat.
- **Steam boilers.** These are recommended when heat is required for processes exceeding 100 °C or for generating steam. Steam boilers have a high efficiency and can be powered by various types of fuels, such as natural gas or biomass, providing greater flexibility in terms of operating costs and sustainability. Additionally, they allow for the recovery of heat from the generated steam, further enhancing their overall efficiency.
- **Industrial microwaves.** This technology has already been implemented on a small scale in Demonstrator 4. Although its use is less common than other heating methods, industrial microwaves provide a valuable option for processes requiring the heating of non-conductive materials or specific treatments, such as material drying. By directly heating materials at the molecular level, microwaves can significantly reduce processing time and energy consumption, especially for dielectric materials like ceramics or polymers.
- **Heat exchangers.** These devices are ideal for harnessing heat generated from other processes or reusing residual heat from exhaust gases. Heat exchangers can also be used in combination with energy sources like steam or hot water, which are generally more efficient than electricity for large-scale heat generation. By capturing and redistributing thermal energy, heat exchangers enhance overall process efficiency and reduce energy costs, making them an excellent choice for industrial scaling.
- **Thermal Solar Panels.** As a renewable alternative, thermal solar panels can be an efficient solution by converting solar energy directly into heat, which can then be stored or used in various processes. While they may not be suitable for all industrial applications due to temperature limitations, thermal solar panels are particularly effective for pre-heating stages or processes requiring low-to-medium heat levels. By leveraging solar energy, they offer a sustainable option that can reduce reliance on conventional energy sources and lower operating costs.

8.3 Use of Variable Speed Drive (VSD) or Variable Frequency Drive (VFD) in air compressors

Given the scale of the trials conducted in the project, with some at laboratory scale, compressed air requirements have been met using the pre-existing compressed air network at the facilities.

For scaling up, the use of air compressors with variable speed drives (VSD) is recommended. Without a VSD, compressors typically operate at full capacity regardless of demand. In contrast, with a VSD or variable frequency drive (VFD), the motor speed is adjusted based on system requirements, reducing unnecessary energy consumption during low-demand periods.

Another advantage of VSDs is that they allow the compressor's operation to be modulated, avoiding periods when the compressor runs idle or without load. This feature enables the compressor to either shut down or reduce speed when full capacity isn't needed, enhancing energy efficiency.

Additionally, VSDs offer benefits beyond energy savings. They extend the compressor's lifespan by smoothing start and stop cycles and by precisely adjusting speed, which improves operating conditions, reduces vibrations, and minimises strain on components.

In terms of process optimisation, VSDs allow for precise control by regulating pressure according to demand. This leads to improved process stability and, consequently, enhanced product quality by reducing the risk of over-pressurisation or under-pressurisation.

All these benefits also contribute to lower operational costs, as energy expenses are reduced during operation, and maintenance costs are lowered due to fewer repairs and less frequent component replacements.

8.4 Renewable installations for electricity production

Some of the demonstrators (1, 3, 7, and 9) are already powered by photovoltaic solar panels. This setup not only helps to minimise the environmental impact associated with electricity use but also reduces operational costs by eliminating the need to purchase electricity from the grid.

However, photovoltaic installations come with the limitation that the electricity generated must be used immediately upon production to be effective. This constraint is similar to other renewable technologies, such as wind installations, which depend on solar irradiance and wind speed as renewable resources. One option to optimise generation is to combine various types of technologies, such as photovoltaic installations, wind power, and solar thermal systems.

To optimise the use of photovoltaic installations, demand management strategies can be employed by adjusting the operation of the prototype to the electrical generation. In this context, the development of management systems based on machine learning is gaining momentum, enabling the prediction of both demand and energy generation. Additionally, artificial intelligence is increasingly utilised to optimise consumption and storage based on predicted energy generation, enhancing the overall efficiency of resource use.

However, most demonstrators required continuous operation times of 24 to 48 hours, which limits the ability to fully align generation with demand. To address this, energy storage strategies are recommended. Various technologies are available for this purpose:

- **Electric Batteries:** This is the most traditional and efficient method of storing energy generated by photovoltaic installations. A major advantage of electric batteries is their high storage efficiency, which typically reaches around 90%. However, investment costs remain a drawback, as despite considerable reductions in recent years, they still limit the profitability of installations. Another disadvantage involves the environmental impact associated with both the manufacturing and, especially, the recycling of batteries once they reach the end of their useful life. While lithium batteries are the most widely used, other battery technologies are available, such as lead-acid and sodium-sulfur batteries.
- **Hydrogen:** In recent years, hydrogen-based technologies have emerged as a promising alternative for energy storage. These technologies produce hydrogen from water and electricity via electrolysis, which can later be converted back to electricity using fuel cells or into thermal energy through combustion. Known as Hydrogen-based Energy Storage Systems (HESS), this technology, though still maturing, offers the significant advantage of long-term energy storage, with fewer energy losses over time compared to electric batteries, which are more prone to charge loss. However, the primary drawbacks are the high investment costs relative to electric batteries and relatively low energy efficiency, typically around 33%.
- **Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES):** This is another emerging technology that utilises solar energy to compress air in large underground reservoirs. When energy is needed, the compressed air is released to generate electricity. These installations are implemented on a large scale to support electrical grids or industrial projects.
- **Thermal Storage Systems:** These systems utilise heat generated by the sun, storing it in materials such as molten salts or water, and releasing that energy to produce electricity when needed. They are primarily used in solar thermal or hybrid installations (photovoltaic combined with thermal). The main disadvantage is the low efficiency in converting stored thermal energy into electricity.

9 Energy performance improvement targets

Setting energy performance improvement targets is a critical step in driving energy efficiency within an organisation. These targets are designed to provide clear goals for reducing energy consumption, cutting costs, and minimising environmental impact. The process of setting these targets should be well thought out, ensuring that the objectives are **ambitious**, **achievable**, and **aligned** with the organisation's broader energy management strategy.

9.1 Aligning targets with KPIs

Energy performance improvement targets should be directly linked to **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)**. These KPIs serve as measurable metrics that provide insights into various aspects of energy consumption and efficiency. For instance, if a KPI is based on **energy intensity** (the amount of energy consumed per unit of output), the target could aim for a specific reduction in that intensity, such as reducing energy consumption by 10% per unit of production over the next year.

The key is to set targets that reflect **specific areas for improvement**, such as cutting energy use in particular processes, reducing overall facility energy consumption, or lowering carbon emissions. Each target must be **measurable**, ensuring the organisation can track progress and assess whether the improvements are being realised.

9.2 SMART Targets

Effective energy performance improvement targets should follow the **SMART criteria**:

- **Specific**: The target should clearly define what is to be achieved. For example, “reduce total energy consumption by 5% in 12 months” is a specific target.
- **Measurable**: The target must be quantifiable. This ensures that the organisation can monitor and verify the progress. Using accurate data from energy meters or sub-meters makes this possible.
- **Achievable**: Targets must be realistic, considering the organisation's current capabilities and resources. Setting overly ambitious goals may lead to frustration or failure.
- **Relevant**: The target should align with the organisation's overall energy strategy and business objectives. It should focus on areas that will make a significant impact.
- **Time-bound**: Every target should have a clear deadline. This creates a sense of urgency and encourages consistent effort toward achieving the goal within the defined timeframe.

9.3 Short-Term vs Long-Term Targets

Organisations should set both **short-term** and **long-term** energy performance targets. Short-term targets might focus on incremental improvements, such as reducing energy

intensity by 3-5% within the next year. These targets help maintain momentum and allow for regular progress assessments.

Long-term targets, on the other hand, are more ambitious and aim for substantial reductions over a period of years. For example, a long-term target could involve reducing overall energy consumption by 20% over five years. These targets often involve larger projects, such as upgrading energy systems or adopting renewable energy sources, which may require significant investment and planning.

9.4 Balancing ambition with realism

While it's important to set ambitious targets, they must also be **realistic**. Targets that are too aggressive may be difficult to achieve, leading to frustration or demotivation. On the other hand, targets that are too conservative may not drive the necessary change to improve energy performance meaningfully. Striking the right balance ensures that the organisation stays motivated while making measurable progress towards its energy goals.

In summary, setting energy performance improvement targets involves careful consideration of KPIs, ensuring that the goals are SMART, and balancing short-term progress with long-term vision. By doing so, organisations can create a structured approach that drives continuous improvement in energy efficiency.

10 Monitoring, Measurement and Verification

For the Energy Management Plan, measurement and verification methods are essential to ensure the effectiveness of energy-saving initiatives and to track progress towards energy goals.

Firstly, a system should be established to **monitor and track energy consumption** regularly. This system will provide real-time insights into energy usage patterns, allowing for timely adjustments and ensuring continuous optimisation.

To accurately capture energy consumption, **metering and sub-metering systems** should be implemented across different areas or processes. These systems will help break down overall energy use into more manageable sections, making it easier to identify where potential savings can be made and to assess the impact of any implemented efficiency measures.

It is important to **define key performance indicators (KPIs)**, which will serve as benchmarks for evaluating progress towards the set energy efficiency objectives. These KPIs should be specific to the areas of focus and reflect meaningful metrics that demonstrate improvements in energy performance.

Regular **energy performance assessments** should also be conducted to evaluate progress taking into account the evolution of the KPIs. These assessments will compare actual energy usage against the defined KPIs and established targets, enabling the identification of any discrepancies and the need for corrective actions. This structured approach ensures that energy efficiency efforts remain aligned with organisational goals and deliver measurable improvements.

All of these points are part of the Plan-Do-Check-Act strategy.

11 Communication Plan

For the effective communication and transparency of the Energy Management Plan, it is essential to establish a clear and consistent reporting and communication strategy.

First, it is necessary to develop a **reporting framework** that will enable the communication of energy performance, achievements, and areas for improvement. This framework should ensure that all relevant information is captured and presented in a clear and concise manner, tailored to the needs of different audiences, including management and key stakeholders.

Regular reports should be provided to management and stakeholders, highlighting key outcomes such as energy savings, cost reductions, and environmental benefits. These reports will not only demonstrate the success of energy efficiency initiatives but also identify areas where further improvements can be made, ensuring continuous progress towards energy goals.

Additionally, it is important to foster a culture of **energy awareness and engagement** within the organisation. Sharing energy-related information with employees helps raise awareness of the importance of energy efficiency and encourages active participation in energy-saving practices. This can be achieved through internal communications, workshops, or energy performance updates, creating a shared responsibility for energy management across the organisation.

By promoting transparency and open communication, the Energy Management Plan will ensure that all parties are informed and engaged, driving further progress in energy efficiency.

12 Conclusions

This deliverable presents an energy analysis of each demonstrator in the project, identifying the equipment that represents the main energy consumption within each process. To pinpoint the products that entail the highest energy expenditure, the energy consumption per unit of product obtained (kilograms or litres) has been used as a KPI, with the products EG, TPA, and Antioxidant extract emerging as the highest energy consumers.

It is worth noting, however, that each demo has been tested at different scales, which may affect the efficiency of the processes and influence the KPIs. Furthermore, a series of opportunities for improving the energy efficiency of the processes were identified during the energy analysis. These measures have been listed and described to serve as a basis for enhancing process efficiency at the scaling stage. Notable measures include: heat recovery from steam generated during processes, selection of more efficient heat generation technologies for heating and drying materials, use of variable speed drives on compressors, and the installation of renewable energy sources with storage capabilities to enable continuous prototype operation.

Subsequently, the objectives for a measurement and verification plan have been outlined, with an emphasis on the importance of defining and monitoring KPIs. Finally, a summary of the objectives for the communication plan within the energy management plan has been provided, focusing on the dissemination of results and the awareness-raising of workers responsible for the processes.

As next steps, in WP6, specifically in T6.2, the energy consumption of the demonstrators will be monitored and analysed, calculating and verifying the KPIs presented throughout this deliverable.

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